

Mathematical analysis and implications of new definition of singular integral operator

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Abstract

Let D be a connected bounded domain in R^2 , S be its boundary which is closed, connected and smooth or

$$S = (-\infty, \infty). \text{ Let } \Phi(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_S \frac{f(s)}{s-z} ds$$

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1. Introduction

Let D be a connected bounded domain on the complex plane, S be its boundary, which is closed and $C^{1,\alpha}$ -smooth, $0 < \alpha \leq 1$ or $S = (-\infty, \infty)$. The standard definition of the singular integral operator

$$Af = \frac{1}{i\pi} \int_S \frac{f(s)ds}{s-t} \text{ is:} \dots\dots\dots(1)$$

We assume that $f \in L^1(S)$. This is the basic new assumption: in the literature it was assumed that $f \in H^\mu(S)$, where $H^\mu(S)$ is the space of Hölder-continuous functions, or $f \in L^p(S)$, $p > 1$, see [2], [4]. In [1] there is a result for $f \in L^1(S)$, the existence of the limit (1) is proved, and the proof is far from simple. Our goal is to give a new definition of the operator A . This definition makes the proof of the existence of Af for $f \in L^1(S)$ very simple. It is also of great interest to have a proof of the Sokhotsky formulas for $f \in L^1(S)$, see also [6].

Definition 1

$$(Af, \varphi) = (f, A\varphi) \quad \forall \varphi \in H^\mu(S), 0 < \mu < 1 \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Here $(Af, \varphi) = \frac{1}{i\pi} \int_S \dots$

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Lemma 1

Formula (2) defines $f \in L^1(S)$ uniquely.

Proof. Suppose that $f_1, f_2 \in L^1(S)$ satisfy (2). Then $q := f_1 - f_2$ satisfies the relation

$(q, A\varphi) = 0$ for all $\varphi \in H_\mu(S)$. It is known [2] that the set $A\varphi | \forall \varphi \in H_\mu(S) = H_\mu(S)$ if $0 < \mu < 1$.

Therefore, $q \in L^1(S)$ is orthogonal to the set $H_\mu(S)$ dense in $L^1(S)$. Consequently, $q = 0$ and

$f_1 = f_2$. Lemma 1 is proved. Q

Let us check that the right side of formula (2) makes sense. This mathematical expression can be written as

$\int_S \int_S f(s)\varphi(t) ds dt$. The integrand here is absolutely integrable over $S \times S$. Therefore, the order of integration can be changed and formula (2) makes sense.

There are other advantages of Definition 1. For example, it is easy to prove that the operator A is closed.

Lemma 2

The operator A in $L^1(S)$ is closed.

Proof. One has to prove that the graph f, Af is a closed set in $L^1(S) \times L^1(S)$. Let $f_n \rightarrow f$ and $Af_n \rightarrow h$, convergence in $L^1(S)$. Then, by Definition 1, $(f_n, A\varphi) = (f, A\varphi) = (Af, \varphi)$ and $(Af_n, \varphi) = (h, \varphi)$. Therefore, $(Af, h, \varphi) = 0 \forall \varphi \in H_\mu(S)$. Since $H_\mu(S)$ is dense in $L^1(S)$, it follows that $Af = h$. Thus, A is closed. Q

However, A is not continuous in $L^1(S)$.

Example 1

Let us show that there is an $f \in L^1(S)$ such that $Af \notin L^1(S)$.

known formula, see [3]: $F(s^{-1}) = \pi \operatorname{sgn}(\xi)$, where $\operatorname{sgn}(\xi) = 1$ if $\xi > 0$, $\operatorname{sgn}(\xi) = -1$ if $\xi < 0$, $\operatorname{sgn}(0) = 0$. The Fourier transform of $f \in L^1(S)$ is a continuous uniformly bounded function. Therefore, $f \operatorname{sgn}(\xi)$ is not, in general, a continuous function at $\xi = 0$. Thus, if $f \neq 0$, then the function $Af \notin L^1(S)$.

2. Other results

- Consider the equation $Af = h, h \in L^1(S)$. From Example 1 it follows that a necessary and sufficient condition for the solvability of this equation in $L^1(S)$ is the condition $h \sim 0$. If this equation is solvable, then its solution is unique. Indeed, if f_1 and f_2 are solutions, then $q = f_1 - f_2$ solves the equation $Aq = 0$. Taking its Fourier transform leads to the relation $q \operatorname{sgn}(\xi) = 0$. Therefore, $q \sim 0$ for $\xi \neq 0$. Since $q \in L^1(S)$, it follows that $q \sim 0$ so $q = 0$ and $f_1 = f_2$. Q
- Let us prove the generalization of the Sokhotsky-Plemelj formulas to the case when

$$f \in L^1(S). \text{ Let } \Phi(z) = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_S \frac{f(s) ds}{s-z}. \text{ Then}$$

$$\Phi(z) = f(t)v(z) + \psi(z), \quad \psi(z) := c \int_S \frac{f(s) - f(t)}{s-z} ds, \quad t \in S, \quad v(z) := c \frac{ds}{s-z}, \quad (3)$$

and

$$v(z) = \begin{cases} 1, & z \in D, \\ \frac{1}{2}, & z \in S, \\ 0, & z \in D^c. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

One has

$$\Phi^+(t) = \lim_{z \rightarrow t, z \in D} \Phi(z) = f(t) + \psi^+(t) \quad (5)$$

where $\psi^+(t) = \lim_{z \rightarrow t, z \in D} \psi(z)$ and

$$\Phi^-(t) = \lim_{z \rightarrow t, z \in D} \Phi(z) = \psi^-(t). \tag{6}$$

If $t \in S$, then one gets (see equation (4), the line $z \in S$):

$$\Phi(t) = \frac{f(t)}{2} + \psi(t) := \frac{f(t)}{2} + c \int_S \frac{f(s) - f(t)}{s - t} ds. \tag{7}$$

The $\psi(t)$ is the value of $\psi(z)$ at $z = t$. The $\psi(t)$ and $\Phi(t)$ are understood as in Definition 1

If some equation holds almost everywhere with respect to the Lebesgue measure on S , then we write that this equation holds a.e.

From formulas (3)–(6) one derives:

$$\Phi_+(t) - \Phi_-(t) = f(t) + \psi_+(t) - \psi_-(t) \text{ a.e., } \Phi_+(t) + \Phi_-(t) = f(t) + \psi_+(t) + \psi_-(t) \text{ a.e.} \dots\dots\dots (8)$$

In Lemma 3 we prove that $\psi_+(t) = \psi_-(t) = \psi(t)$ a.e. Therefore, formula (8) can be rewritten as:

$$\Phi_+(t) - \Phi_-(t) = f(t) \text{ a.e., } \Phi_+(t) + \Phi_-(t) = f(t) + 2\psi(t) \text{ a.e.} \dots\dots\dots (9)$$

From equation (9) it follows that

$$\Phi_{\pm}(t) = \Phi(t) \pm \frac{f(t)}{2}, \quad \Phi_-(t) = \Phi(t) - \frac{f(t)}{2}, \text{ a.e.} \tag{10}$$

where $\Phi(t) = \psi(t)$. Formulas (10) are the Sokhotsky-Plemelj formulas for $f \in L^1(S)$.

Theorem 1

For $f \in L^1(S)$ formulas (10) hold.

To finish the proof of Theorem 1 it is sufficient to prove Lemma 3.

Lemma 3. If $f \in L^1(S)$ and S is $C^{1,\alpha}$ -smooth, $0 < \alpha \leq 1$, then

$$\psi_+(t) = \psi_-(t) = \psi(t) \text{ a.e.} \dots\dots\dots (11)$$

Before proving Lemma 3 we prove Lemma 4.

Lemma 4

One has

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{1}{s - t \pm iN_\epsilon} = \frac{1}{s - t} + \pi \delta(s - t). \tag{12}$$

Proof. Formula (12) is understood according to Definition 1. Let $f \in L^1(S)$, $\varphi \in H_\mu(S)$, N_t be a unit normal to S directed inside D . Then Furthermore,

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_S \frac{d\varphi(t)}{s - t - iN_x\epsilon} \frac{f(s)ds}{s - t - iN_x\epsilon} := \int_S \frac{d\varphi(t)}{s - t - i0} \int_S \frac{f(s)ds}{s - t - i0}.$$

Furthermore,

$$\int_S \frac{d\varphi(t)}{s - t - i0} \int_S \frac{f(s)ds}{s - t - i0} = \int_S \frac{d\varphi(t)}{s - t} \int_S \frac{f(s)ds}{s - t} + i\pi \int_S \varphi(t)f(t)dt, \quad \forall \varphi \in H^\mu(S), \quad (13)$$

and

$$\int_S \frac{d\varphi(t)}{s - t} \int_S \frac{f(s)ds}{s - t} = \int_S dsf(s) \int_S \frac{\varphi(t)dt}{s - t} \quad \forall \varphi \in H^\mu(S). \quad (14)$$

We have proved formula (12) according to Definition 1 with the minus sign. Similarly one proves this formula with the plus sign. Lemma 4 is proved. Q In [3], p. 83, there is a formula $1 = 1 + i\pi\delta(x)$ understood in the sense of distributions.

$x-i0 \quad x$

The formula in Lemma 4 is of the similar type. The Sokhotsky-Plemelj formulas (10) were

derived in [2] and [5] under the assumption that $f \in H^\mu(S)$. Under such an assumption, these formulas hold everywhere, not almost everywhere.

Proof of Lemma 3

By Definition 1 one has (neglecting 1 and denoting by integration

over $S \times S$):

$$\lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \int_S \int_S \frac{[f(s) - f(t)]\varphi(t)}{s - t \pm iN_x\epsilon} ds dt = \int_S \int_S \frac{[f(s) - f(t)]\varphi(t)}{s - t} ds dt \pm i\pi \int_S \varphi(t) f(t) dt \quad (15)$$

where

$$J := \int_S \int_S [f(s) - f(t)]\varphi(t)\delta(s - t) ds dt = \int_S \int_S [f(s) - f(t)]\varphi(t)\delta(s - t) ds dt = 0. \quad (16)$$

For $f \in H^\mu(S)$ formula (16) is trivial by the standard definition of the delta-function. For $f \in$

for $f \in L^1(S)$. Lemma 3 is proved. Q

Let $z \in D$. The following question is of interest:

When is the boundary value $\Phi_+(t)$ of $\Phi(z)$ on S equal to f a.e.?

Equation (10)

Yields a necessary and sufficient condition for this:

$$\Phi_+(t) = f(t) \text{ iff } \Phi(z) = 0, z \in D^- \text{ and } f(t) = \Phi(t) + f(t), \text{ or } f(t) = 1 \int_S f(s) ds \text{ a.e.}$$

If one wants to formulate a necessary and sufficient condition for $f(s) \in L^1(S)$ to be boundary value of an analytic in D^- -function $\Phi(z)$, $\Phi(\infty) = 0$, then an argument, similar to the above yields the following conditions:

$$f(t) = -\frac{1}{i\pi} \int_{s \neq t} \frac{f(s)}{s-t} ds \quad \text{a.e.} \quad (17)$$

If equation (17) holds, then $\Phi_+(t) = 0$ and, consequently, $\Phi(z) = 0$ if $z \in D^+ = D$.

Remark 1

If $\Phi(t) = f(t)$ a.e., $f \in L^1(S)$, then $Af \in L^1(S)$, where $Af := f(s) ds$ a.e. If $-\Phi_-(t) = f(t)$ a.e., $f \in L^1(S)$ and $\Phi(\infty) = 0$, then $Af \in L^1(\text{Supp } S - t \in L^1(S))$. Since for some $f \in L^1(S)$ one does not have $\Phi(z) = 0, z \in D^-$, it follows that not every $f \in L^1(S)$ is a boundary value of an analytic function in D .

3. Conclusion

A new definition of singular integral operator in $L^1(S)$ is given. Sokhotsky-Plemelj formulas are derived for $f \in L^1(S)$. Other results are obtained.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to disclosed.

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